

CONCEPTUALIZATION OF FACILITY MANAGEMENT IN THE HOTEL BUSINESS

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Topicality. Facility management saves time and effort, and thus ensures the efficiency of basic and supporting business processes. Therefore, the simplification of business processes through facility management has become an important component of economic policy in the hotel business and the research object. The relevance of the study is to identify the main aspects of facility management in the hotel business as an organizational function based on scientifically sound concepts. **The purpose and methods.** The purpose of the study is a theoretical analysis of facility management as a management technology, determining the determinants of its implementation in the economic activity of the hotel business. The multidisciplinary and multidimensional nature of the scientific problem has led to the application in the research process of a set of general scientific methods, such as abstraction, analysis and synthesis, inductive and deductive, historical, logical, method from abstract to concrete. **Results.** The etymology of the term «facility management» has been studied and the most relevant definition has been defined. The basic concepts of facility management of hotel business entities have been considered. The basic directions of application of facility management in activity of hotels depending on various factors and the purposes of activity have been defined and considered. **Conclusions and discussions.** The research showed that the conceptualization of facility management in the hotel business is an urgent scientific task, as it allows studying and scientifically substantiating the directions of optimization of individual business processes, which is necessary in a competitive environment. Further research needs to be deepened to assess the effectiveness of the use of facility management in hotels in Ukraine.

Key words: hotel, facility management, information architecture, management standard.

The relevance of the problem

Problem formulation. Transformational economic processes in Ukraine cause significant sectoral changes, actualizing the implementation of innovative technologies in the management of hotel businesses, which are now an important component of the tourism system. Currently, the operation of the hotel industry is carried out in conditions of latent economic instability. This requires the innovative concepts introduction of business process management, rapid management decisions to prevent possible «failures» in the main, security, technological and managerial business processes. That

is why in the management of complex infrastructure facilities, which include hotel chains and independent hotels, actively implemented technologies of building management (life cycle management of buildings and structures), property management (administrative and legal property management), asset management (financial flow management) and facility management (FM) (infrastructure management).

State study of the problem. in the scientific literature, the essence of building, property and asset management has been studied and developed in the format of applied recommendations (Chotipanich, 2004; Potkany et al., 2015; Okolie et al., 2011; Croal et al., 2003; Hassanien & Losekoot, 2002). Regarding FM in the hotel business, it was found that international hotel chains, including Marriott, Hilton Hotels and Resorts, Carlson Rezidor Hotel Group, Ramada Encore and Premier Hotels and Resorts, show stable trends of successful development, linking these positive results with the use of technology just FM (Espino-Rodríguez & Ramírez-Fierro, 2018; Sylvester, 2014, "Ohliad ukrainskykh hoteliv i restoraniv", n. d.). At the same time, scientific research practically lacks theoretical and methodological bases for the application of management technologies in the hotel business. in particular, scientific controversy is over the choice of management tools, which, given the diversity of infrastructural components, diversity of business processes, can be the basis for the correct choice of management tools to achieve a balance of basic, security, technological and management business processes.

Unresolved issues. The relevance of the research is to determine the main aspects of management directly in the hotel business and the choice of a particular type of facility management in the hotel as an organizational function based on scientifically sound concepts.

Purpose and research methods

The purpose of the article is to study and theoretical analysis of FM as a management technology, to determine the determinants of its implementation in the economic activity of the hotel business.

Research methods. The interdisciplinary and multifaceted nature of the scientific problem has led to the use in the study of a set of general scientific methods: abstraction, analysis and synthesis, inductive and deductive, historical, logical, convergence from abstract to concrete, which provided a systematic nature of the determinants of FM.

The information base of the research was the scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists, whose achievements reveal the managerial essence of facility management, features of application and effectiveness in terms of its impact on business processes.

The object of research is the process of implementation and realization of facility management in the hotel business.

The subject of research is the features of facility management in the hotel business.

The scientific novelty is to define the conceptual foundations and directions of facility management in the hotel business, which will ensure effective management of the enterprise by providing quality hotel services and achieving new levels of competitiveness.

Research results

World experience shows that the presence of professional management in the hotel business is one of the most important factors influencing its market attractiveness.

Thus, the results of the International Business Survey Grant Thornton ("Autorsoring: put k effektivnosti i rostu", 2014) show that currently use or plan to use FM services 40% of medium and 43% – large businesses, where there is an effect of scale and expected high results.

The results of a comparative analysis of scientific work on FM testify to the systematic research on the formation of theoretical, methodological and applied basis of this management technology: in the scientific works of Y. Adevunmi and O. Ogunba (2006) studied the evolution of FM; G. Cairns (2003) – the philosophical basis of service management in the FM system; K. Alexander (1993; 2013) – proposed the formation and evaluation of FM; K. C. Okolie, F. I. Emoh, P. Ogunoh (2011) – summarizes the practical experience of applying this concept in the management of the life cycle of the object.

Some scholars limit the socio-economic perspective of FM, considering it as part of the management system of the object (building), in particular M. Potkany, M. Vetrakova, M. Babiakova (2015) and a little earlier – T. Thomson (1990) A. Speeding (1999), D. Shiem-Shin Then (1999), J. Hinks and M. Puybaraud (1999) and others.

Despite the diversity of research on FM, it is worth noting the fragmentary and debatable theoretical and methodological developments for the implementation of their results in the management of hotel businesses. The analyzed scientific works do not allow forming a holistic basis of this concept in the field of hotel business, which limits the possibilities of using FM tools to achieve socio-economic goals of the hotel business.

These arguments determine the scientific position on the relevance of the study of the determinants of FM in the hotel business, the subjects of which are characterized by multi-orientation of business processes. Understanding the determinants of FM is also aimed at establishing a balanced subject-object relationship between the infrastructural elements of the hotel. These research accents have their own scientific significance, as they form the organizational and conceptual basis of the scientific essence of FM in the hotel business in order to develop practical recommendations that will be designed in the plane of hotel operation, which will provide a new quality of management.

The seriousness of the approach in the global dimension is confirmed by the implementation of the Standard of facility management (ISO 41011, ISO 41012, ISO 41001) by the European Commission for Standardization (CEN) (2020). Therefore, the conceptualization of FM will make it possible to outline the prospects for its development in the Ukrainian market, the capacity of which is currently problematic due to the mixing of terminology.

Based on the results of the analysis of the scientific sources and normative documents covered by this research, certain definitions of this type of management can be distinguished (*table 1*).

As it can be seen from the table, the borrowed concept of «facility management» has undergone some changes, losing, in particular, the social and financial components. The modern definition of the term «facility management» is fixed in the international standard ISO 41001: 2018: «Facility management is an organizational function that unites people, places and adjusts processes inside the building to improve the quality of life and productivity of core business» ("Facility management", 2018). Thus, unifying these approaches, we can distinguish their architectural elements: people (management), processes (communication, integration), objects (place, technology). Therefore, we propose to define facility management as a holistic management system that communicates jobs and integrates them into ancillary business processes and technologies.

Tabl. 1. The scientific field of the definition of “facility management”

Model	Definition
American	Coordination of workplaces with the work of the organization, integration of enterprise economics, architecture, personnel management; activities that cover processes to provide a functional environment built through the integration of people, places, processes and technologies
German	Consideration, analysis, optimization of costs, processes related to the object, carrying out works not related to the main activity of the enterprise
Polish	A comprehensive strategic program to keep all systems and subsystems in constant readiness in accordance with changing requirements
Ukrainian	Management of the organization’s infrastructure (real estate, engineering and social infrastructure of the organization) and ensuring the provision of necessary business services

Source: developed by authors on the bases K.C. Okolie, F.I. Emoh and P. Ogunoh (2011); Z. Chen (2015); Y. Adewunmi and O. Ogunba (2006); A.V. Talonov (2020)

Implementing this provision in the domestic practice of the hotel business, to prevent syllogism, it is worth noting certain features of the term «facility», used to mean «convenience» in describing the category of hotels and rooms, as well as the quality of hotel infrastructure. At the same time, in combination with other words, “facility” forms a number of terms that help to understand certain aspects of this concept that are used in management (Thomson, 1990):

- *community facilities;*
- *educational facilities;*
- *housing facilities;*
- *office facilities.*

Thus, facility management is a management system that includes processes to ensure the viability of the hotel as a holistic complex, which allows you to optimize business processes (Fig. 1).

According to fig. 1 FM covers the following areas: management (business process management: revenue and expenditure management, distribution of financial flows, market positioning; management of legal aspects of relations with stakeholders, consumers; management of social aspects); technical (maintenance and development of real estate, its maintenance and operation, organization of protection, cleaning, coordination of redevelopment and reconstruction); social (outsourcing of staff, management skills and experience, etc.).

Thus, FM uses management technologies that can be fully or partially outsourced, which reduces the internal costs of maintenance and operation of the hotel ("Ohliad ukrainskykh hoteliv i restoraniv", n. d.; Lysiuk & Tereshchuk, 2016). The role of hotel owners and management will be to administer the implementation of FM functions and innovative development of support and additional business processes. The tasks set before FM they are quite diverse from technical support of the object (building management) to financial flow management, profit maximization, and increase the cap-

italization of the object (asset management). Thus, the tasks assigned to FM in the management system of the hotel entity are a hierarchical structure (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Some directions of implementation of the hotel management facility

Source: developed by the authors

Fig. 2. Tasks of facility management in the structure of hotel management

Source: Developed by authors based on K. C. Okolie, F.I. Emoh and P. Ogunoh (2011);
Z. Chen (2015); Y. Adewunmi and O. Ogunba (2006); A.V. Talonov (2020)

To successfully perform these tasks, you need to properly organize the management process. Therefore, the effectiveness of the FM technologies use should be investigated at several levels of information architecture: strategic, tactical and operational (Fig. 3).

Based on Fig. 3, it can be stated that for effective facility management of the hotel there must be organized relational forms, effective organization, initiative general manager; effective data-based management system, management style (maintenance, facility management), quality hotel service and relationship management.

		<i>functions</i>	<i>aims</i>	<i>concepts</i>
FM	Strategic	- direct facilitation - service management - activity management	- income growth - productivity - level support	- strategy integration
	Tactical	- implementation - control and monitoring - designing - management	- achievement - satisfaction with the result - implementation	- initiative - integration - planning
	Operative	- realization - service	- cost minimization - fulfilling of needs - quality	- efficiency - quality assurance

↑
simple
experienced

Fig. 3. Information architecture of the hotel management facility

Source: developed by the authors on the basis of S. Chotipanich (2004); Y. Adewunmi and O. Ogunba (2006); N. E. Myeda (2014)

Thus it is possible to allocate such kinds of FM («Fasiliti menedzhment. Proshloe. Nastoiashchee. Budushchee», 2018):

- *internal*: creation of own division in hotel which is responsible for service and auxiliary processes;
- *integrated*: a full range of measures for the management and maintenance of the hotel facility;
- *outsourcing*: transfer to management of third-party organizations of service or support processes under certain conditions of the contract.

The choice of a particular type of FM depends on many factors (Fig. 4).

Contextual analysis of FM components (support, business development, information and technology, facility management tools and tools, management style and marketing) showed that approximately 40% of hotels in Ukraine outsource maintenance management and 60% practice full-fledged FM. At the same time, if maintenance is combined with the management of hotel facilities, the overall success is achieved in 80% of hotels (Cairns, 2003). Thus, effective FM is aimed at maximizing the potential of the hotel's property assets.

At the same time, it is important for hotels to use new ways to implement the functions and goals of FM, which form a qualitatively and quantitatively higher value: intellectual and information innovations. These solutions provide the opportunity to significantly optimize costs and increase the efficiency of all business processes.

Conclusions and discussion of results

The results of the study showed that the conceptualization of hotel facility management is an urgent scientific task, because it allows studying and scientifically substantiating the directions of optimization of individual business processes, which is necessary in a high level of competition. The decision to choose a variable configuration in the information architecture of management is focused on benefiting from the integration of FM in the hotel. The use of hotel property assets improves the comfort and safety of both consumers and hotel staff, thereby increasing the possibility of optimizing resources and ensuring an increase in the load factor of the number of rooms.

Fig. 4. Influencing factors on the choice of a certain type of facility management in a hotel
 Source: own development

Further research needs to be deepened in order to assess the facility management practices effectiveness in the activities of hotels in Ukraine in the event of natural disasters, man-made disasters, pandemic risks, etc.

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КОНЦЕПТУАЛІЗАЦІЯ FACILITY МЕНЕДЖМЕНТУ У ГОТЕЛЬНОМУ БІЗНЕСІ

Актуальність. Facility менеджмент дозволяє заощадити час та зусилля, а отже, забезпечити ефективність основних та підтримуючих бізнес-процесів. Тому питання спрощення ділових процесів за допомогою facility менеджменту стали важливою складовою економічної політики у готельному бізнесі та об'єктом дослідження. Актуальність дослідження полягає у визначенні основних аспектів facility менеджменту у готельному бізнесі як організаційної функції, заснованої на науково обґрунтованих концепціях. **Мета і методи.** Мета дослідження полягає у теоретичному аналізі facility менеджменту як управлінської технології, визначення детермінантів його імплементації у господарську діяльність суб'єктів готельного бізнесу. Багатодисциплінарна та багатовимірна природа наукової проблеми призвела до застосування у процесі дослідження набору загальнонаукових методів, таких як абстракція, аналіз та синтез, індуктивний та дедуктивний, історичний, логічний, метод від абстрактного до конкретного. **Результати.** Досліджено етимологію терміна «facility management» та встановлено найбільш актуальне визначення дефініції. Розглянуто основні концепти facility менеджменту суб'єктів готельного бізнесу. Визначено та розглянуто основні напрями застосування facility менеджменту в діяльності готелів залежно від різних факторів та цілей діяльності. **Висновки та обговорення.** Дослідження показало, що концептуалізація facility менеджменту в готельному бізнесі є актуальним науковим завдан-

ням, оскільки дозволяє вивчити та науково обґрунтувати напрями оптимізації окремих бізнес-процесів, що є необхідним в умовах конкуренції. Подальші дослідження потребують поглиблення з огляду оцінки ефективності практики використання facility менеджменту в готелях в Україні.

Ключові слова: готель, facility менеджмент, інформаційна архітектура, стандарт управління.

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КОНЦЕПТУАЛІЗАЦІЯ FACILITY МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В ГОСТИНИЧНОМ БІЗНЕСЕ

Актуальность. Facility менеджмент позволяет экономить время и усилия, а следовательно, обеспечить эффективность основных и поддерживающих бизнес-процессов. Поэтому вопрос упрощения деловых процессов с помощью facility менеджмента стали важной составляющей экономической политики в гостиничном бизнесе и объектом исследования. Актуальность исследования заключается в определении основных аспектов facility менеджмента в гостиничном бизнесе как организационной функции, основанной на научно обоснованных концепциях. **Цель исследования** заключается в определении факторов влияния на концептуальный выбор направлений facility менеджмента в гостиничном бизнесе. **Методы исследования.** Многодисциплинарная и многомерная природа научной проблемы привела к применению в процессе исследования набора общенаучных методов, таких как абстракция, анализ и синтез, индуктивный и дедуктивный, исторический, логический, метод от абстрактного к конкретному. **Результаты.** Исследована этимология термина «facility менеджмент» и установлено наиболее актуальное определение дефиниции. Рассмотрены основные концепты facility менеджмента субъектов гостиничного бизнеса. Определены и рассмотрены основные направления применения facility менеджмента в деятельности гостиниц в зависимости от различных факторов и целей деятельности. **Выводы и обсуждение.** Исследование показало, что концептуализация facility менеджмента в гостиничном бизнесе является актуальной научной задачей, поскольку позволяет изучить и научно обосновать направления оптимизации отдельных бизнес-процессов, что необходимо в условиях конкуренции. Дальнейшие исследования требуют углубления с точки зрения оценки эффективности практики использования facility менеджмента в гостиницах в Украине.

Ключевые слова: гостиница, facility менеджмент, информационная архитектура, стандарт управления.